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THE FORMATION OF SYNTACTIC PARADIGMATICS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the formation of the phenomenon of syntactic paradigmatics. It presents several considerations on how the study of conjunctive sentence transformations within the framework of syntactic paradigms gained its academic status in later years. Such studies are also found in global linguistics, including Russian and Uzbek linguistics—mainly emerging after the theory was introduced by D. Worth. In Uzbek linguistics, we can also observe that syntactic paradigmatics, including its complex forms based on compound sentence structures, has been scientifically substantiated in the research of many scholars.

Key words: syntactic paradigmatics, compound sentence, complex syntactic structures, transformation, applicative model, transforms.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola sintaktik paradigmatika hodisasining shakllanishiga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, unda qo'shma gaplarning transformatsiyasini sintaktik paradigma doirasida o'rganish keyingi yillarda o'z ilmiy maqomiga ega bo'lganligi haqida mulohazalar bildiriladi. Bunday tadqiqotlarga jahon tilshunosligida, xususan, rus va o'zbek tilshunosligida ham duch kelamiz. Ayniqsa, D. Uort tomonidan sintaktik paradigmatika nazariyasi e'lon qilinganidan keyin ushbu yo'nalish faol rivojlana boshladi. O'zbek tilshunosligida ham sintaktik paradigmaticaning, ayniqsa qo'shma gap materiallariga asoslangan murakkab shakllari bir qator olimlar tadqiqotlarida ilmiy asosda yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sintaktik paradigmatika, qo'shma gap, murakkab sintaktik qurilmalar, transformatsiya, aplikativ model, transform.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена формированию феномена синтаксической парадигматики. В ней рассматриваются некоторые соображения о том, как изучение трансформаций союзных предложений в рамках синтаксической парадигмы приобрело свой научный статус в последующие годы. Подобные исследования встречаются и в мировой лингвистике, в том числе в русском и узбекском языкознании, в основном после провозглашения теории синтаксической парадигматики Д. Уортом. В узбекском языкознании также можно отметить, что синтаксическая парадигматика, включая её сложные формы, основанные на материале сложносочинённых предложений, была научно обоснована в трудах ряда исследователей.

Ключевые слова: синтаксическая парадигматика, сложносочинённое предложение, сложные синтаксические конструкции, трансформация, аппликативная модель, трансформы.

INTRODUCTION

In the previous sections of our work, we discussed how the phenomenon of syntactic paradigmatics is inherently connected to transformation processes as well as morphological tools. In this section, we will explore complex syntactic paradigms formed on the basis of compound sentence models. It is important to emphasize that there has been limited specialized research focused specifically on syntactic paradigmatics within the context of compound sentence structures.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of compound sentence transformation as a syntactic paradigm has only recently garnered significant attention. Such research—both globally and within Russian and Uzbek linguistics—began to take shape predominantly after D. Worth's formulation of syntactic paradigmatics. In Uzbek linguistics, A. Berdialiyev has made substantial contributions to the understanding of syntactic paradigmatics, particularly with regard to its intricate expression in compound sentence structures. His scholarly works, including monographs, specialized

course texts, and methodological manuals—such as Foundations of Uzbek Syntactic Paradigmatics, Paradigmatic Syntax of the Uzbek Language, and Semantic-Significative Paradigmatics in Complex Sentences with Subordinate Clauses—have played a pivotal role in analyzing the paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships of linguistic units within Uzbek. In the following discussion, we examine some of Berdialiyev's key perspectives, particularly regarding syntactic paradigmatics. He begins by elucidating foundational concepts such as position and invariant, which are essential for understanding paradigmatic relationships:

“Paradigmatic relations are those in which linguistic units are interchangeable within a specific position. For instance, in pairs such as house—building, road—street, work—task, and in series like to the child – to the student – to the worker, or slave – wealthy person – cattle owner, laborer – worker, this interchangeability is evident. In the first three examples, the units occupy the same position due to their synonymy, while in the others, they function within the same syntactic position...”

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to Berdialiyev, paradigmatic relations exist at all levels of language and involve at least two units, where the variants function as members of a paradigm and are subordinated to an invariant unit. For example, *kitob* (book), *kitobning* (of the book), *kitobda* (in the book), *kitobga* (to the book), and *kitobdan* (from the book) constitute the case paradigm of the word *kitob*. Each of these forms serves as a variant within the overarching paradigm, collectively reflecting the grammatical structure and relational potential of the base unit.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study of transformational paradigms formed from compound sentences was initiated in our earlier research. For instance: Zumrad is being asked about by the factory owner renowned throughout the city (*Oybek, Ulug'yo'l*). A) The factory owner who is famous throughout the city is the one inquiring about Zumrad. B) Zumrad is being asked about by such a factory owner whose fame has spread throughout the city^[4]. In his specialized course, A. Berdialiyev elaborates on paradigmatic relations by distinguishing between oppositional features among paradigm members, which ensure the existence of a paradigm. He writes: “Members of a paradigm possess both similar and differing traits. These distinctions form the basis of oppositionality, which is essential for the paradigm's structure and for the survival of language elements”^[3].

He provides examples demonstrating this in both morphological and syntactic paradigms, such as: *O'qidim, o'qiding, o'qidi* (I read, you read, he/she read); *Maktab, maktabning, maktabni, maktabga, maktabdan* (school in different cases); *Nodir lives with us – Nodir wants to live with us – If Nodir had lived with us* (changing modality and tense). According to Berdialiyev, for a syntactic paradigm to form, it must consist of two or more elements that: a) exhibit oppositional relations; b) can be derived from one another; and c) include invariant and variant members. Thus, compound sentence models (e.g., two-part vs. one-part, complete vs. incomplete, coordinated vs. uncoordinated) may all exhibit these features. Berdialiyev also emphasizes that while compound sentence paradigms share features with simple sentence paradigms, they present specific complexities—such as internal oppositions and multiple derivations. For example: *The weather became cold and the ground froze – When the weather became cold, the ground froze; Anyone who works honestly is respected – Whoever works honestly, that person is respected*^[3]. In the second example, distinguishing the invariant is difficult due to the equal semantic weight of both versions. Introducing a simple sentence like *An honest worker is respected* provides an invariant, but it creates a mixed paradigm rather than a purely compound one. Compound sentences also serve as the basis for forming the formal paradigms of simple sentences. Each clause in a compound sentence forms its own internal paradigm, contributing to a layered syntactic paradigm structure. For example: *Thick snow and severe cold covered the rivers so heavily that not only horses and camels, but also carts loaded with heavy goods moved easily on the ice* (*P. Qodirov*). Alternative renderings reflect different internal paradigmatic structures. Some researchers define compound sentence paradigms using the verb's tense category, as seen in L.Yu. Maksimov's work. N.N. Matveyeva, working with English material, identifies tense, modality, and affirmation-negation as paradigm-forming elements^[5,6].

Berdialiyev divides compound sentence paradigms into: formal-structural paradigms related to the expression level of language; semantic-significative paradigms related to the content level. For example: *Spring came and fieldwork began – When spring came, fieldwork began*. The former reflects structural variation within synonymous expressions, while the latter addresses paradigms based on differences between coordination (*parataxis*) and subordination (*hypotaxis*). He also stresses that the sentence is the principal unit of syntactic paradigmatics. Therefore, constructions like *The student read* (sentence) vs. *The student's reading* (phrase) should not be equated in paradigmatic analysis.

CONCLUSION

We fully agree with Berdialiyev's assertion that the sentence is the core unit of syntactic paradigmatics. However, when discussing the system of syntactic paradigmatics, it is unnecessary to classify paradigm members separately. Whether addressing word-group paradigms, simple sentence paradigms, or compound sentence paradigms, one must avoid conflating these distinct categories.

In conclusion, the phenomenon of syntactic paradigmatics is inextricably linked to transformation. Transformation serves as the central mechanism in the formation of syntactic paradigms and functions as a fundamental method in syntactic derivation. In other words, syntactic derivation involves not only the applicative method but also—crucially—the transformational method.

References:

1. Berdialiyev, A. (1989). Semantic significative paradigmatics in compound sentences with predicative clauses. Tashkent.
2. Berdialiyev, A. (1990). Paradigmatic syntax of the Uzbek language (Methodical recommendation). Leninabad.
3. Berdialiyev, A. (1991). Foundations of syntactic paradigmatics in the Uzbek language. Tashkent.
4. Turniyazov, N. K. (1971). Attributive subordinate clauses in Uzbek and French languages (Abstract of candidate dissertation). Tashkent, pp. 9–10.
5. Maksimov, L. Yu. (1968). On the paradigmatics of complex sentences with subordination. Russian Language at School, (1).
6. Matveeva, N. N. (1984). The problem of paradigmatics in complex sentences with subordination (based on modern English). Leningrad, p. 136.
7. Turniyazov, N., & Khayrullayev, Kh. (2007). On methods of structural analysis and the theory of transformation. Foreign Philology, (1), p. 45.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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